

6. SaxFDM-Tagung

20-21 November 2025
Dresden, Germany

ACHIEVEMENT BADGE

S

Storage of Data

I backup my research data regularly and store it securely to prevent data loss.

H

Handling of Persistent Identifier

I own a persistent identifier, such as an ORCID id, that allows others to find my work easily.

A

Accessibility of Data and Metadata

I'm using open data formats and Metadata Standards to enhance the accessibility of my research data for a wider audience.

R

Repository for Publishing Data/Software

I publish data / software in a public repository and provide a reusable-friendly license, such as CC-BY or Unlicense.

E

Electronic Lab Notebook

I document my research in an electronic lab notebook (e.g., eLabFTW), including metadata and links to my data for enhanced organization and accessibility.

Instructions:

- 1. Identify Achievements**
Each letter corresponds to a specific achievement and task.
- 2. Cross the Letter**
Cross out the letter when you completed the task in your daily work.
- 3. Celebrate Success**
Share your achievements with your team and colleagues!
Discuss your accomplishment!

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S H A R E

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✓ ✓ A ✓ E

